

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH ONYM COMPONENTS

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Abstract: This article discusses the department of onomastics and phraseological units with onomastic components. This is given the components of onomastics which are anthroponyms, toponyms, zoonyms. Clearly, onomastic components were used in their direct meaning but later, it had figurative meaning being as a component of phraseological units.

Keywords: onomastics, onomastician, anthroponyms, toponyms, zoonyms, ethnonyms, glottonyms, proper names, figurative meaning, nominative function, representative function, dominant, onomastic component, phraseological unit, proverb.

In the field of linguistics onomastics is the study of proper names, especially the names of people (anthroponyms) and places (toponyms). A person who studies the origins, distribution, and variations of proper names is an onomastician. George Redmonds defines names as "...special words that we use to identify a person, an animal, a place or a thing, and they all have a meaning. In many cases that meaning will lie concealed in the name's history, but in others it will still be transparent." (Redmonds, 2007: IX) The term onomastics comes from Greek 'onoma' and it means *name*. William Bright (2003) implies, such study is carried out as part of some larger fields like linguistics, ethnography, philology, history, philosophy, etc [3.4].

He says, people use when they refer to almost everything (e.g. "*Banana* is the name of the fruit."). He notices, in this example, the word 'name' is almost synonymous with the word 'noun'. Bright distinguishes two principal types of proper names: personal names or *anthroponyms* and place names or *toponyms* (other varieties also exist, such as *ethnonyms*- terms referring to nationalities or ethnic groups; and *glottonyms*- referring to languages). Cecily Clark says that proper names are words without meaning; they make no sense because they have lost their meaning. They are words without connotation and are typically used to refer to individuals. She continues with the explanation that, before a descriptive formation becomes a 'name', it must be separated from its etymological meaning "in such a way that the sound-sequence, no matter how complex its structure or plain its surfacemeaning, becomes a simple pointer" (Clark, 2005: 452). The tradition of giving names to persons, Clark

states, comes from West-Germanic people. Their custom required that each individual should have a single, distinctive name [3.5].

Modern researchers emphasize that the onomastic subsystems of the language are part of the linguistic pictures of the world: "The description of the onomastic picture of the world, based on the study of the principles of naming, the creation of a dictionary of onomastic vocabulary and the establishment of a list of realities that have been honored with the name, will, to a certain extent, allow us to approach the creation of a common inventory of connotative symbolic systems that determine different directions of the human spirit "[9.21]

In modern linguistics, the question of the structural and semantic structure of the English anthroponymic dictionary remains open and unexplored. The subject of the research is the ways of representing English anthroponyms in the English anthroponymic dictionaries of the British, American and Russian editions [9.22].

The linguists A.B. Suslov and A.B. Superanskaya, "the role of a personal name in a person's life is very great. Each person can only be called by name, therefore all his good and all his bad deeds are made public thanks to his name". Therefore, some names are dearly loved by the people and are used very often, while others, on the contrary, cause complete disgust and negative emotions associated with its bearer. Being an integral part of the life of any person, personal names, as part of the language system, have attracted the attention of researchers for a long time. As a result of this interest, a special section of onomastics has developed - anthroponymics, which studies the names of people [9.25].

When translating such proper names, one must take into account the context of their use. A competent translator should not indulge in statements such as "Threw lightning arrows", or "Moses led the people of Israel in the desert for forty years," or "King James was on the throne for two years"[

Let's make a few comments about the translation of English geographic names. With them, the situation is simpler, because in case of doubt, the translator can refer to the English-Russian regional geographic dictionary, where he will find the names of most countries, states, counties, regions, cities, etc. In general, the transfer of geographical names is carried out on based on the same priorities as the "translation" of people's names: preference is given to transcription. Wed: the city of Tucson "translates" as Tucson. However, we will give a few examples when there may be some doubts about the translation of a

particular name. Underlying doubts in most cases are resolved with the help of a dictionary[3.19].

Toponyms are linguistic signs of the natural language, indicating certain fragments of the topographical space. These linguistic signs form a system that is artificially contractual in character and called a toponymic system (toponymy). Toponyms are a kind of repositories of the political, social and cultural views of society, in which "certain language trends, peculiarities of word formation and word changes" are displayed. According to the dictionary-reference of linguistic terms, the word toponymy is formed from two Greek words (topos"place, locality" and onoma"name", i.e. "referring to the name").

Toponymic vocabulary is a unique cognitive-pragmatic means of cognition, accumulation, reflection, storage, transmission and evaluation of the phenomena of the surrounding world. Toponyms are linguistic signs of the natural language, indicating certain fragments of the topographical space. The toponymic layer of vocabulary is characterized by many processes and phenomena inherent in common names such as semantic variation, word formation, motivation, internal form. Motivated nominations, figurative meaning (metaphor and metonymy), a pragmatic aspect.

The toponym has both a linguistic and a speech meaning. The value is represented mainly by the denotative component, which indicates the correlation of the toponym with the designated object; the significative component, which is associated with the ability to denote the denotation of an entire class of objects, also occurs in certain language contexts. In addition, as in common vocabulary, the connotative (pragmatic) component is distinguished in the structure of the meaning of toponymic vocabulary, as an emotionally expressive and evaluative reflection of objects of the external world. Important is also the linguodidactical trend of toponymic research, since the study of language should occur in close connection with the knowledge of culture, history, traditions of the people speaking this language[6.20].

Zoonyms are assigned to animals" proper names or nicknames. Zoonomia is the youngest area of onomastics that deals with the nicknames of animals. Many authors build animals" nicknames on the play of words, consonances, associations, or subtexts. Formal designations of animals often acquire the status of their names in the tales. In this case, they are written with a capital letter and used without the article (for example, Cat, Dog, Goat, Frog) although corresponding to a particular item occur no less frequently.

Sometimes, the use of the name without the article, as it were, finally fixes the transition of the nominal designation in the IF[4.56].

The phraseology of a living natural language can not do without onyms -it is toponym, zomimics, phythonimics, krematonimik, chrononymics, ergonomics, astronomer, anthroponymics, etc., i.e. Onomasiology as the theory of nomination studies all units of language in terms of realization. They are nominative, or representative function. Phraseological units has an important place in the world linguistics as national and cultural units.

The study of phraseological units in a comparative-typological aspect will serve as a source in subsequent research in the field of comparative linguistics. In the research of the above-named researchers, phraseological units are analyzed in linguocultural, semantic, structural terms. However, phraseological units with an onomastic component in English, Russian, and Uzbek have not been studied semantically. In our study, we analyzed the meaning and content of phraseological units with onomastic components on the example of different structural languages[1.56].

This proverb with irony applies to those who abstain from eating and drinking and spend all their money for getting dressed. The toponym «Margilan» is used to reinforce the meaning of irony[2.6].

Conclusion: The onomastic components of the phraseological units of the Uzbek language served to express various semantics. It should be noted that these semantics can be understood primarily through the names that come from the phraseological units. In addition, the dominance of a particular sema depends on the centuries-old customs and traditions of the peoples who speak that language.

References:

1. AlenkaVrbinc, MarjetaVrbinc. (2014)Phraseological unitswit onomastic components: The case of English and Slovene, University of Ljubljana.
2. Gallimulina L.T. Phraseological units with an onym component in Uzbek, English and Russian languages,. Fergana State University. International engineering journal for research & development, 2021, 2-6 p.
3. Ivan Fijok . Onomastics as evidence of linguistic influence. Osijek. 2012. 2-38 p
4. Azizova F.S. (2018). Lingua-cultural features of teaching phraseological units in the Uzbek language to the students of higher educational establishments (under the examples of English and Uzbek languages): The dissertation thesis (PhD). - Tashkent, -p. 56.

5. GaniyevaSh.A (2017). The structure of Uzbek phraseologisms (modelling by form and meaning): The dissertation thesis (PhD). - Fergana, - p. 50.
6. SharipbayevaA.M, Zhassarova D.G, Word-formation specifics and usage of toponyms in modern English language, 2019,
7. <https://scienceforum.ru/2019/article/2018014789>
8. Juraeva I.A Lexical - semantic features of anthroponyms in English language, Journal of Contemporary issues in Business and Government, 2021.11, 65 p.
9. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356568224>
10. Enazarov T, Allanazarova S.X, Stylistics of proper nouns on Uzbek artistic onomastics, Newsletter of KhorazmMamun Academy, Khiva-2020, 75-76p
11. Егорова Т. П. Семиотическая функция имени // Ономастика. Материалы к серии Народы мира и культура. – Вып. XXV.- Ч. I. – М.: РАН, 1993. – С. 21-28.

